

Environmental Sensitivity Index Mapping around Vishakapatnam (Vizag) Coastline

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ABSTRACT

This paper discusses the prediction of oil spill Vulnerability and Environmental Sensitivity Index (ESI) mapping of part of the vishakapatnam coast have been using by the QGIS. ESI is aimed to rank the shoreline on the basis of their sensitivity to oil spill and present it in map. In this work, remote sensing imagery of sentinel-2 sensor has been used to delineate vulnerable assets such as forest, crop land, mangrove cover, tidal flat, estuary, exclusive economic zone, exclusive biodiversity zone, major fishing zone. Using the NOAA guidelines of ESI mapping each sub-category has been ranked on a oil spill vulnerability index scale of 1 to 10 where 1 represent least vulnerable and 10 maximum vulnerable. The ranked categories were colour coded as per the NOAA guideline in GIS environment and a ESI map has been generated. This map is very important and may be used for spill response contingency planning

Keywords: vishakapatnam coast, Environmental Sensitivity Index, GIS, GNOME, Vulnerability, Trajectory model, Oil spill.

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

Fossil fuel such as oil is the major source of energy. Oil is drilled from wells that are situated in the privileged countries around the world. These countries, transport the crude oil to other needy countries through the sea route mainly. Many important oil wells are located at off-shore. the coast, which is situated at the Bay of Bengal. Due to the proximity to Gulf countries, Bay of Bengal has become major oil transportation route and that is the reason it is vulnerable to oil spill. in case of a blowout in the well (such as in deep Horizon), oil can spill at very fast pace. Spill mainly occur due to leakage in the oil tankers, leakage in oil pipe lines, off shore oil exploitation, well blowout, natural seepage, cleaning of drilling mud, deliberate discharge from oil refineries etc. Oil owing to low density is having tendency to float over the water surface that can reach at the coastline under the influence of waves or tides. Shorelines are often very rich in biodiversity thus oil spill reaching the shoreline can drastically damage the existing ecological balance at the shoreline. Coastlines are populated by mangroves, sediment dwellers, estuarine ecology and of various other flora and fauna which are responsible for making balance between ocean and continental part.

A large oil spill can disrupt the delicate balance of shoreline ecosystem and may potentially cause long term problem..

METHODOLOGY

Ancillary data

Published Biodiversity map of coast, Geological map

Satellite data

Sentinel2satellitedataofMarch,2019

Software Used

QGIS and GRASS

Study Area

The study area is part of state which is bounded by Bay of Bengal. This part of the state of vishakapatnam lie near East Godavari district and it constitute beaches around the city of in addition to rich mangrove forest. The area is under the administrative limits of district vishakapatnam.

Methodology For Lulc Classification

Satellite Remote Sensing is capable of sensing object in terms of spatial resolution, temporal resolution, radiometric resolution and spectral resolution. These capability along with GIS is making it possible to locate different land form unit, various land use land cover pattern present. It can be done either visually by using FCC image or digitally by using some software. In this present study the FCC image has been classified digitally in QGIS-GRASS software. Using several band combination and proper filtering image has been categorized into 13 classes.

Table.1: Classification of Accuracy

Class Name	Referenc e Totals	Classifie d Totals	Number Correct	Producer s Accuracy (%)	Users Accur acy (%)
fallow land	11	10	8	80.64	85.00
recreational Land	8	10	7	76.50	78.00
vegetation	9	10	7	77.78	79.00
Salt farm	9	10	7	77.78	78.00
mangroves	10	10	8	80.00	90.00
River	12	10	10	83.33	98.00
water body	13	10	10	79.23	90.00
settlement	11	10	8	78.64	77.00
Beach	10	10	9	83.00	90.00
Sea	8	10	8	80.00	86.00
Port	7	8	8	78.00	80.00
Coastal vegetation	10	10	8	80.00	80.00

Parameters required for the study:

1. Ecological parameters: Land forms, Oil sensitive organisms, Mangroves.
2. Geological parameter: Soil type, Grain size of beach sand, Geomorphology, Slope of the shoreline.
3. Shore line parameter: High vulnerability, Medium, Low.
4. Land use land cover: Man-made features, agricultural land, aquaculture, tourism spots, wetlands, sandy beaches.
5. Biological parameter: Diversity of marine species along the coastline, Breeding, nesting, resting, feeding sites of some important organisms.
6. Human use resources: Port area, Industrial site.

Environmental Sensitivity Index ESI Mapping (ESI)

ESI maps are prepared in advance to tackle the oil spill hazard. Similar to a susceptibility map, it identifies shoreline as per the degree of sensitivity to oil spill and rank them as per the NOAA guideline.

The Construct of ESI Mapping

The ESI system is founded on following three broad parameters:

- a) Shoreline Classification – Classified and ranked as per relative sensitive to oil spill, natural persistence of oil, cleanup ease.
- b) Biological Resources – The flora and fauna that are sensitive to oil in addition to their supporting environment such as coral reefs.
- c) Human or Physical Resources – Manmade areas such as parks, beaches, water intakes, marine sanctuaries and other recreational sites along the shoreline that has induced sensitivity.

EXPERIMENT AND RESULT AND DISCUSSION

With visual interpretation and digital image classification various thematic maps such as Shoreline type map, mangrove cover map, tidal flat map, landform map, drainage maps are created. Maps showing biological features and socioeconomic features are also prepared with the help of supplied data. Further DEM data has been downloaded from USGS site and slope map, aspect map and terrain maps are created. Here we used image classification technique to classify the sandy beaches, vegetative beaches, port area, islands. Hope island which lies just off the city coast, it naturally acts as a barrier and protects the city from various effects.

Shore line, type found in Vishakapatnam coast by visual interpretation of satellite data are, rocky head land, rocky shore, sandy beaches, sheltered rocky shores. Land form found through image interpretation are, estuaries, headlands, beaches which varies from coarse to fine, creeks, tidal flats, mud flats, islands. Substrate type along the shore line are mainly coarse sand, fine to medium sand, fine sand, rocky. It is identified which can be vulnerable if oil spill will coincide with the high tide. They are given ranking according to the given reference in NOAA guideline.

Shore line, type found in Vishakapatnam coast by visual interpretation of satellite data are sandy beaches, vegetative beaches. Land form found through image interpretation are estuaries, headlands, beaches which varies from coarse to fine, creeks, mud flats, islands. Substrate type along the shore line are mainly coarse sand, fine to medium sand, fine sand, rocky.

- ESI 10 The highest sensitivity rank of 10 Mangrove, swamps, fresh water marshes .
- ESI 9 Ranking 9 is beaches and water streams connected to sea.
- ESI 8 Ranking 8 is Port area and fishing zone, industry.
- ESI 7 Ranking 7 is Exposed rocky tidal flats, are given this ranking.
- ESI 6 Ranking 6 is awarded to salt pans and they are present in all over the coastal area.
- ESI 5 Ranking 5 awarded to land settlements such as houses.
- ESI 4 Ranking 4 Coarse grained beaches are they were not present there.
- ESI 3 Rank 3 is awarded fine to medium grained beaches.
- ESI 2 ranking 2 Rocky shore, scraps.
- ESI 1 Rank 1 is given to the exposed rocky shores and exposed solid man made structures.

GNOME Model

GNOME model used for prediction of oil spill trajectory ,GNOME is developed by the Hazardous Materials Response Division (HAZMAT) of the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration Office of Response and Restoration (NOAA OR &R), USA.

The General NOAA Oil Modeling Environment (GNOME) is a two-dimensional model that designed for the rapid modeling of pollutant trajectories in the marine environment it's used as forecasting tool for both spill events and a planning tool to examine in it .

GNOME uses an Eulerian/Lagrangian spill-trajectory model in which the regional physics are simulated as Within GNOME the oil is divided into a small particles which move under the influence of ocean currents, wind drift and turbulent motions. The fate and transport of oil spilled into the marine environment also depends on a suite of physical, chemical and biological processes “weathering”.

Trajectory modeling

The oil spill trajectory simulation using the GNOME model because of its high prediction accuracy in The model is based on Langrangian discrete element which enables the simulation behavior of oil spill during the breaking process that includes spreading, evaporation, dispersion, and advection. The model is used of simulating different types oil spill such as gasoline, diesel, medium oil, and kerosene at different volume and conditions such as continuous spill, instantaneous ship leak, intentional tank discharge, and leakage of tank.

Vulnerability mapping

The vulnerability of the coastal resources to oil spill was ascertained using the shoreline resources properties layer that comprises of socio-economic, biological and physical shoreline features of the coastal area and the GNOME trajectory output from the twelve oil spill scenarios during the three climatic seasons.

The index of vulnerability was categorized into five classes

1 .very-high , 2. high , 3. moderate , 4. low , and , 6. very-low.

The very low index represents areas the least in vulnerability to oil slick spots concentration.

CONCLUSION

This study has been aimed to carry out oil spill vulnerability ranking and mapping of part of vishakapatnam area using geospatial tools. High resolution sentinel 2 satellite imagery has been used to identify the sensitive areas. The work emphasizes the importance of geospatial tool the preparation of ESI map. Remote sensing and GIS provides fast and cheap way to find out the different classes of shoreline present in the coast. GIS provides powerful cartographic tool and data updating facility. Sensitivity of the vishakapatnam coast may be considered as medium to high. There are sandy head lands and pristine fragile beaches which attracts tourists from all over the world. Estuarine eco system will be most affected if the oil spill coincides with the high tide. These estuaries are having Mangroves which are rich in biodiversity. It is suggested to have pre-validated ESI maps for our Indian coast in response to action and contingency planning for oil spills in India. The coastline of vishakapatnam which is having tidal variation of 6.4m is at risk during the oil spill because of its estuarine ecology and fragile beaches. During the high tides, a potential spill may reach up to 30 to 40 km inside the river. This ESI map means to support the environmental planners at the time of oil spill.

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